

Charge transfer complex of *p*-phenylenediamine and *p*-chloranil

Mukesh Paliwal^a, M. L. Kalra^b and Suresh C. Ameta^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, ^bDepartment of Physics, M. L. Sukhadia University,

Udaipur-313 001, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : ameta_sc@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The charge transfer (CT) complex of *p*-phenylenediamine and *p*-chloranil was prepared in acetonitrile by solution growth, diffusion and microwave methods. The CT complex was characterized by its elemental analysis. IR and ¹H NMR spectral studies. The data obtained indicated the formation of 1 : 1 CT complex between the compounds. The d.c. electrical conductivity of the CT complex showed the semiconductor behaviour of complex at room temperature.

Keywords : Charge transfer complex, d.c. electrical conductivity, *p*-phenylenediamine, *p*-chloranil.

Introduction

The Lewis acid-base molecular complexes¹ between organic molecules, or an organic molecule and inorganic molecule, have received considerable attention in connection with the studies of the mechanism of electric conduction by organic compounds. Investigations of one-dimensional conductors began with the successful growth of single crystal of organic charge transfer complex formed between tetrathiafulvalene as an electron donor and tetracyanoquinodimethane as an electron acceptor (TTF-TCNQ)^{1,2}. Field of conducting organic compounds has provided a promising new generation of functional materials for future technology. Various applications including thin films application and molecular electronic devices³ are currently under active development. Recent advances in novel molecular-scale engineering include switching and memory systems^{4,5}, Schottky and electroluminescent diodes^{6,7}, field effects transistors^{8,9}, photovoltaic devices and solar cells¹⁰, rechargeable batteries, non-linear optical devices thermistors and negative-resistance¹¹. Charge transfer complexes of TCNQ with some drugs^{12,13} such as ofloxacin, levofloxacin, lomefloxacin, pipemidic acid, ciprofloxacin, norfloxacin, perfloracin and fleroxacin show better antibacterial and biological activities than the parent drugs and this makes them pharmaceutically more important.

Some of the charge transfer complexes containing

chloranil (CA) as an acceptor are TTF-CA¹⁴, TTF-imidazole-CA¹⁵, *p*-phenylenediamine-CA¹⁶, TMPD-CA¹⁷, aniline-CA¹⁸, aromatic amines and nitrogen heterocycles-CA¹⁹, *N*-aryldithiocarbamates-CA²⁰, phosphine oxide and tri-*n*-butyl phosphate-CA²¹ etc.

It was proposed to prepare CT complex of *p*-phenylenediamine with *p*-chloranil by different methods like solution growth, diffusion and microwave exposure method and to study their electrical conducting behaviour at room temperature.

Results and discussion

The elemental analysis and spectral data suggested that all complexes correspond to 1 : 1 stoichiometric ratios of donor and acceptor, respectively.

The general behaviour of d.c. electrical conductivity obeys the relation $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$, where σ_0 is constant, E_a is the activation energy of conduction process, T is the absolute temperature and k is the Boltzmann constant. The room temperature d.c. electrical conductivity of the complex lies in the range 1.96×10^{-10} to 20.50×10^{-6} S cm⁻¹ and it depends on the method of preparation of charge transfer complex. It indicates that the chemical composition of the complex remains same in all the three methods used, but there are some changes in the crystals of this complex, so that the conductivity is lowest (10^{-10} S cm⁻¹) in the crystals prepared by solution growth method but on the other hand, it is 10^5 times

higher in the complex prepared under microwave exposure.

The formation of the charge transfer complex was also confirmed by ^1H NMR spectra. In *p*-phenylenediamine, a singlet of NH_2 appeared at δ 4.06 and singlet of four aromatic protons was found at δ 6.21, whereas in CT complex, these values get shifted to δ 5.41 and 7.52, respectively.

In the IR spectra, it has been found that the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{Cl})$ of acceptor (*p*-chloranil) are shifted to lower wave numbers as a result of the increased electron density on the acceptor as compared to its free state. On the other hand, in the donor molecules the N-H stretching frequency of NH_2 group is shifted to higher wave number. Appearance of a broad band at 3446 cm^{-1} in the CT complex also indicates the presence of an intermolecular hydrogen bonding.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade. *p*-Chloranil (E. Merck) and *p*-phenylenediamine (S. D. Fine) were used for synthesis and their solutions were prepared in dry acetonitrile (CDH) as solvent. Acetonitrile was dried over dry silica for one day, refluxed for 5 h over P_2O_5 and distilled through a fractionating column. The middle fraction (b.p. $82\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) was collected in air-tight bottles.

Melting point of complex prepared was determined in an open capillary and is uncorrected. A domestic microwave oven (Kenstar, Model OM-26 EGO) of 2450 MHz frequency, with a maximum power of 900 Watt was used. The elemental analysis (C, H and N) of compound was performed on a Vario-EI III-Carlo-Erba 1108 analyzer. Purity of the compound was checked by TLC using a mixture of amyl alcohol : pyridine : water (3 : 2 : 1.5) as mobile phase, on silica gel coated glass plates and spots were visualized by exposing the dry plates to iodine vapours. The CT complex was stable in the mobile phase. IR spectra were recorded by preparing KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 1800 (FT-IR) spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX spectro-meter (300 MHz) using CDCl_3 or MeOD, using and TMS as an internal standard.

The d.c. electrical conductivity was measured in the pellet form using manually constructed furnace, Keithly's autoranging picoammeter, Systronics twin power supply, Keithly's 155 null detector micro voltameter, Toshniwal self adjustable autotransformer (Variac), TWG KONTACT

thermometer and EPOCH's μ -AMICOMP UPS.

For good crystal growth, slow rate of growth and minimum disturbance such as temperature variation, mechanical variation, intermittent intense light exposure, slow nucleation, extremely clean and dry container with highly purified and dried solid precursors were used for synthesis purpose.

Procedure :

In the solution growth method of synthesis²², the acceptor and donor solutions were prepared in dry acetonitrile in 1 : 1 ratio and heated to effect dissolution. The mixture was allowed to cool slowly in thermocol box filled with insulating material. After a month or more, black crystals with metallic shine were deposited on the walls of the beaker, which were washed with acetonitrile and collected. The product was recrystallised from methanol.

In the diffusion method²³, solid *p*-chloranil was placed in compartment A (Fig. 1) and *p*-phenylenediamine in compartment B. Then purified acetonitrile was poured in part C of assembly. This assembly was kept into refrigerator for two months. Shiny black particles were found deposited on the donor side of assembly.

Fig. 1. Apparatus for diffusion method.

In the microwave method, the acceptor and donor solution (in dried acetonitrile) were mixed in a 1 : 1 ratio and irradiated in microwave oven for 60 s (in 6 parts of 10 s each) at power 80 Watt (240 MHz). The reaction mixture was cooled for 5–10 min after every 10 s of heating and irradiated again. A beaker half-filled with water was placed inside the oven to act as a heat sink. The mixture was kept on bench top until the solvent was evaporated.

Elemental analysis :

Found : C, 40.20; H, 1.95; O, 7.20. Calcd. C, 40.67; H, 2.25; O, 7.90%.

This elemental composition indicates that the charge transfer complex formed is 1 : 1 type i.e. one donor molecule is utilized with only one acceptor molecule, in forming the complex.

¹H NMR spectrum :

Following signals appeared in ¹H NMR spectrum of complex, δ 5.41 (4H, s, NH₂), 7.52 (4H, s, aromatic-CH).

IR spectra :

p-Phenylenediamine : IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 3361, 3314 (NH str.), 3010 (Ar. CH str.), 1593, 1510 and 1473 (Ar-C=C str.) and 815 (1,4-disubst.).

Chloranil : IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 1685 (C=O), 1573, 1555 (Ar. C=C str.) and 748 (C-Cl bending).

CT complexes : IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 3446 (O-H), 3315, 3295 (NH str.), 3000 (Ar. CH str.), 1700 (C=O) and 786 (C-Cl).

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